

**FIRST RECORD OF HIPPOSIDEROS KHAOKHOUAYENSIS
(CHIROPTERA: HIPPOSIDERIDAE) FROM VIETNAM**

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Abstract. This note presents the first record for *Hipposideros-khaokhouayensis* in Vietnam. The species is a medium-sized leaf-nosed bat, and differs externally from all other hipposiderids previously known in the country by the shape of its internarial septum, characteristics of skull and teeth. External and cranial measurements for the Vietnamese specimen are compared with published data and taxonomic remarks are provided. Information on the echolocation calls and ecological notes for the species are also given.

Key words: Leaf-nosed Bat, *Hipposideros khaokhouayensis*, Vietnam, new record.

1. Introduction

Leaf-nosed bats Hipposideridae Miller Gray, 1907 are poorly studied. In 2003, fourteen leaf-nosed bat species, including one endemic and mono-specific genus, *Paracoelops* Dorst, 1947, were confirmed to occur in Vietnam [2,8]. Of these, eleven species belong to the genus *Hipposideros* Gray, 1831, including *Hipposideros larvatus* which is believed to comprise a species complex [10]. While studies are required for confirmation, hipposiderid bats within the country may therefore include both *H. larvatus* and *H. grandis*. Two additional hipposiderids, *H. bicolor* and *H. fulvus*, are also included in older publications for Vietnam [7]. While [2] regard these records as misidentifications, they have subsequently been included in recent checklists for Vietnam without critical assessment [3]. In the absence of voucher specimens however, the existence of these two species in Vietnam cannot be confirmed and must therefore be considered questionable.

Between April 2006 and June 2008, field surveys were carried out at several localities within the Cat Ba Biosphere Reserve, north-east Vietnam. During the surveys, a single adult male of an unusual hipposiderid bat was encountered. Analysis of morphological and echolocation data indicate that the specimen captured represents *Hipposideros khaokhouayensis*, a newly described species from Central Lao PDR [9]. Since the species is previously known only from the type locality, Phou Khao Khouay National Biodiversity Conservation Area, the record from Cat Ba Biosphere Reserve represents the first record outside of the type locality and the first record for Vietnam.

2. Content

2.1. Materials and methods

2.1.1. Field Surveys

Located adjacent to the Ha Long Bay World Heritage site in North-Eastern Vietnam, Cat Ba Biosphere Reserve (20°47'42"N, 107°00'38"E) forms part of an archipelago internationally renowned for its spectacular drowned karst landscapes. The biosphere reserve covers 26,241 ha and an altitude range of -39 to +332 metres above sea level (m a.s.l.) and includes 366 islands, with most of the larger islands covered by evergreen subtropical monsoon forest (UNESCO). Cat Ba represents the largest Island within the reserve and encompasses the boundaries of a national park: Cat Ba National Park. The National Park provided the focus for our field surveys and contains terrestrial, freshwater and marine ecosystems which support a diverse range of habitats including humid forests over limestone karst and a range of natural and anthropogenic subtypes, together with subterranean habitats, freshwater wetlands, mangroves and coral reefs (UNESCO).

Four-bank harp traps [6], mist nets and hand nets were employed during the field surveys. Harp traps and mist nets were set across trails within the forest and at cave entrances. Hand nets were used within caves and in open areas. A minimum number of selected individuals were retained as voucher specimens and preserved in 70% ethanol.

2.1.2. Morphological Measurement

External and craniodental measurements were taken to the nearest 0.01 mm, using digital callipers and an OLYPUS SZ4060 stereo-microscope. Methodologies for measurements follow [1,4], except for ear width which follows [5]. Body mass (in gram) was recorded to nearest 0.1 g using a Pesola 50 g scale. Body mass (in gram) was recorded to nearest 0.1 g using a Pesola 50 g scale.

Craniodental measurements were as follows: GTL: greatest length of skull, taken from the tip of the premaxillae to the lambda; CCL: condylo-canine length, from an exoccipital condyle to the anterior alveolus of a canine; SL: skull length, taken from the occiput to the anterior part of the canine; ZB: zygomatic breadth,

the greatest width of the skull across the zygomatic arches; BB: breadth of braincase, taken at the posterior roots of the zygomatic arches; MW: mastoid width, the greatest distance across the mastoid region; PC: post orbital constriction, taken at the narrowest point; C-M³: maxillary toothrow length, from the most anterior part of the upper canine to the back of the crown of the third upper molar; M³-M³: posterior palatal width, taken across the outer borders of the posterior upper molar; C¹-C¹: anterior palatal width, taken across the outer borders of the upper canine; C-M₃: mandibular toothrow length, from the most anterior part of the lower canine to the back of the crown of the third lower molar; M: mandible length, from the most posterior part of the condyle to the most anterior part of the first lower incisors. The specimen (T.070108.1) is housed in the collection of Vu Dinh Thong, the Institute of Ecology and Biological Resources, Hanoi, Vietnam.

2.1.3. Sound Recording and Analyses

Echolocation signals from the captured individual were recorded in the hand, at rest and in flight within a flight tent, and from other non-captured individuals in flight in the wild. Between January and May 2008, acoustic surveys were undertaken on nine nights, with three hours spent each night. Recorded signals were analyzed using custom-made sound analysis software (Selena), developed by the Animal Physiology Department of Tuebingen University, Germany. A variety of echolocation parameters of each signal were measured including the constant-frequency (CF) component. Methods for recording and analyses will be detailed in forthcoming publications.

2.2. Results and discussion

2.2.1. Description and Taxonomic Notes

Table 1. External measurements (in mm) of H. khaokhouayensis from Vietnam and Lao PDR

Measurements	Specimens	
	<i>H. cf. khaokhouayensis</i> , Cat Ba, Vietnam (T.070108.1)	<i>H. khaokhouayensis</i> , Lao PDR, n=8 (Servent & Francis, 2006)
Forearm length	41.36	45.54-48.55
Tibia length	17.14	20.16-22.07
Tail length	34.66	34.95-37.51
Ear length	22.74	24.36-25.24
Ear width	17.3	-
Horseshoe width	5.43	5.23-6.72
Hind-foot length	5.66	7.10-8.27

Length of head and body	42.94	44.13-49.98
Body mass	6	7.7-9.6
CF (in kHz)	94.2	87.2-91.1 (n=6)

Table 2. Selected cranial and dental measurements (in mm) of *H. khaokhouayensis* from Vietnam and Lao PDR

Measurements	Specimens	
	<i>H. cf. khaokhouayensis</i> , Cat Ba, Vietnam (T.070108.1)	<i>H. khaokhouayensis</i> Lao PDR, n=8 (Servent & Francis, 2006)
Greatest skull length*	19.09	18.89 - 19.81
Mastoid width**	9.43	9.86 - 10.37
Zygomatic width*	8.64	9.42 - 9.93
C ¹ -C ¹ width*	3.75	3.95 - 4.31
M ³ -M ³ width*	5.89	6.12 - 6.47
C-M ³ length (at crowns)*	6.02	6.41 - 6.74
Mandible length (from condyles)*	10.74	11.63 - 12.24
C-M ₃ (at crowns)*	6.25	6.76 - 7.25
Postorbital constriction (PC)**	3.04	2.73 - 3.03
Condyllo-canine length (CCL)*	15.72	-
Skull length (SL)**	17.72	-
Breadth of brain-case (BB)*	9.59	9.84 - 10.41
Palatal length**	2.81	2.39 - 2.86

Morphological characteristics and measurements of the specimen from Cat Ba correspond well with the type description of *H. khaokhouayensis* [9] (Tables 1 & 2). The species differs externally from all hipposiderid bats hitherto known from Vietnam by the characteristics of its noseleaf. In particular, the internarial septum expands into a oval disc-like structure (Figure 1). There are no supplementary leaflets. The posterior leaf is narrower than the intermediate leaf. On the frontal margin of the anterior leaf, there is a narrow median emargination. Ears are in uni-

form brown in color and long and broad with bluntly pointed tips. The pelage is brown, with long dark brown hair on the dorsal surface and paler brown on the ventral surface.

Note: * - illustrated in the Figure iii-v [1] ; ** - illustrated in the Figure iv [4].

In general, the specimen collected from Cat Ba Island, Vietnam is smaller than the ones from Lao PDR [9]. Further data are given in the Table 2.

Figure 1. Living specimen of *H. khaokhouayensis* (T.070108.1) from Cat Ba National Park

2.2.2. Echolocation

In all situations including (handheld, whilst bat are flying in their habitats, etc.), peak frequencies of the CF signals of bat populations living in Cat Ba National Park are around 94.2 kHz.

2.2.3. Reproduction

Nothing is known as yet regarding reproduction of *H. khaokhouayensis* in Vietnam. Of females from Lao PDR captured in three different months: February, May, and June; only one in May and another in June possessed enlarged pubic nipples and were lactating. The female captured in February lacked obvious pubic nipples and evidence of lactation [9].

2.2.4. Ecological Notes

The single specimen of *H. khaokhouayensis* was captured by hand net while flying around a building near the May Bau Ranger Station (20°47.599'N, 107°01.046'E; ca. 248 m a.s.l.), on 7 January 2008. May Bau Ranger Station is located in the core-zone of the national park, and is surrounded by primary forest covering on limestone areas (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Habitats at Cat Ba National Park where *H. khaokhouayensis* was captured

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